

Quantum Kinetic Energy As Substance or a Measure of Change of Spatial Frequency?

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. and S.P.N. Messina Dec. 3, 2019

In classical physics, there is energy conservation $KE(x)+V(x)= E$ ((1)), so both kinetic and potential energies have the appearance of a 'quantity' or 'substance'. In bound state quantum mechanics, ((1)) holds, but is based on an unusual average i.e.

$$1/2m (\text{Sum over } p \ p^2 \ f_p \ \exp(ipx)) / (\text{Sum over } p \ f_p \ \exp(ipx)) + V(x) = E \quad ((2))$$

Thus, $KE(x)$ appears as an average in quantum mechanics, with each p momentum state contributing. The problem comes in interpreting this average as f_p may oscillate in p (i.e. be positive or negative, $\exp(ipx)$ is oscillatory, and $(\text{Sum over } p \ f_p \ \exp(ipx))$ may oscillate in x , i.e. be positive or negative. Thus, it is possible to have a p state contribute a value with a negative weight times $p^2/2m$. If $p^2/2m$ is a quantity or substance, it is difficult to interpret this negative contribution to the average. In fact, the particular p state is removing kinetic energy in such an interpretation. In this note, we consider $\exp(ipx)$ as representing a two channel system connected periodically in space and try to interpret p state kinetic energy not as a quantity, but in terms of rates of change of $\exp(ipx)$. Even though kinetic energy or simply momentum of a p state may be related to a rate of change, the average may still be linked to spatial density or changes in density in the system and so this is also investigated.

Negative Plane Wave Kinetic Energy Contribution

In quantum mechanics, one usually deals with the observables density $= W(x)^2$ for a bound state and kinetic energy density $W(x) (-1/2m \ d/dx \ d/dx) W(x)$. Dividing the latter by the former, however, yields a kinetic energy at a point x which satisfies a classical conservation of energy equation i.e.

$$-1/2m \ d/dx \ d/dx) W(x) / W(x) + V(x) = E \quad ((3))$$

If one writes $W(x)= \text{Sum over } p \ f_p \ \exp(ipx)$, then ((3)) becomes equivalent to ((2)). In such a case, each p momentum state contributes a kinetic energy of $p^2/2m$ with a weight $f_p \ \exp(ipx) / W(x)$. For the case of a ground state oscillator $f_p=A\exp(-ap^2)$ and $W(x)=B\exp(-bx^2)$, but in other cases, f_p may oscillate (i.e. become positive or negative with changing p) and $W(x)$ may oscillate (become positive or negative with changing x). Furthermore, $\exp(ipx)$ is oscillatory. For quantum oscillator states above the ground state there are oscillations and for a particle in a box with infinite potential walls, both f_p and $W(x)$ oscillate in terms of their respective variables. Thus, even if one takes only the real part of the weight i.e. $f_p \ \cos(px)/W(x)$, this may be positive or negative for different p or x values. If kinetic energy is thought of as a quantity or substance, it should be such at every level. $\exp(ipx)$ is considered to be a physical p momentum state, thus if $p^2/2m$ has a negative weight, it is difficult to understand. It is as if one has 'anti-kinetic energy', so perhaps kinetic energy should not be thought of as a quantity or substance. Simply because there is a conservation equation such as ((1)) does not mean kinetic and potential energy are quantities, it seems.

How may one interpret kinetic energy of a p state in such a case? First of all, one may consider $p^2/2m \exp(ipx)$ as $-1/2m d/dx d/dx \exp(ipx)$. It seems $\exp(ipx)$ may represent a two channel system linked in space in a periodic manner. Thus, 'p' seems to represent a spatial frequency. The two channels are represented by $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ and $-d/dx d/dx$ of each is the negative curvature or change in the change in each as one moves from x to $x+dx$. In such a case, there is no picture of kinetic energy as a quantity. Rather it is a measure of the rate of change of the change in the weights of the two channels as one moves through space. Then, there is no problem with an interpretation of a negative weight being associated with a particular $p^2/2m$. In quantum mechanics, one uses the operator $-1/2m d/dx d/dx$ to obtain kinetic energy, but then perhaps thinks of kinetic energy in a classical way and assumes it is a quantity. The operator is simply a method to obtain the value of the kinetic energy. In this note, we try to argue the operator may be linked directly to the physical interpretation of kinetic energy.

It should be noted that an average of p state kinetic energy is not the only quantity in the conservation equation ((2)), there is also the potential. It should be possible to describe it in terms of spatial frequencies as well. In particular, if one writes $V(x)$ as a Fourier series then $V(x) = \text{Sum over } k \quad V_k \exp(ikx)$. Thus, for a specific k , as one moves from x to $x+dx$, the contribution changes in a way related to the spatial frequency k i.e. $V_k \exp(ikx)(1+ikdx)$. Alternatively, one may write:

$$-1/2m d/dx d/dx W + V(x)W(x) = E W(x) \quad ((4))$$

and describe $V(x)$ and $W(x)$ as separate Fourier series. In such a case:

$$p^2/2m f_p + \text{Sum over } k \quad V_k f_{(p-k)} = E f_p \quad ((5))$$

Thus, the combination of the Fourier transform V_k of the potential with various Fourier transforms f_{p-k} , i.e. various $p-k$ momentum states, is related to the change in the change of the two channel system. It seems there is no need to think in terms of energy as a substance or quantity.

Furthermore, for the total average energy E , one ultimately has the factor $\exp(iEt)$, which suggests E itself plays the role of a frequency. E represents a specific resonance value as one has a discrete set of eigenvalues for the Schrodinger equation. Thus, not any frequency leads to a resonance.

Role of Average Momentum

In one thinks of kinetic energy of a momentum state p as representing the change in the change of $\exp(ipx)$, then momentum should be $-i$ times the change in $\exp(ipx)$ in space. In classical physics, however, momentum is m times velocity which implies an explicit physical flow. If momentum state p kinetic energy is thought of in terms of a change in the change in $\exp(ipx)$ and momentum in terms of a change in $\exp(ipx)$ in space, how is the average momentum (averaged over the p states in a quantum manner) i.e.

$$(\text{Sum over } p \quad p f_p \exp(ipx)) / (\text{Sum over } p \quad f_p \exp(ipx))$$

linked to flow? One may argue that kinetic energy is not a substance or quantity, but average momentum should still have an interpretation related somehow to physical flow.

Consider d/dx spatial density = $2 W(x) d/dx W(x) = 2$ spatial density $(d/dx W / W)$ ((6))

In such a case, a change in the spatial density of a bound system (an observable) is related to the average momentum $d/dx W / W$. Thus, even though the p momentum state momentum is obtained from $-id/dx \exp(ipx)$ and is related to the change in space of the two channels, the average is still physically linked to a change in spatial density and so a type of flow interpretation seems to still hold.

Thus, it seems that in quantum bound systems, one is dealing with spatial frequencies and changes linked to $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ and fp and $W(x)$ may be periodic as well, and one is looking for a resonance state ultimately linked to the frequency E , nevertheless there are still implications for physical quantities such as spatial density.

In particular, to examine how this occurs, consider the following.

$P(p) P(x/p) =$ probability to have a momentum state p in the bound system multiplied by the conditional probability that given p , the quantum particle is at x .

This should equal $P(x) P(p/x)$. From the above, we have argued that $P(p/x) = fp \exp(ipx)/W(x)$. Then writing $P(x/p) = W(x) \exp(ipx)/fp$ leads to a possible solution of:

$$P(p) = fp^2 \quad \text{and} \quad P(x) = W(x)^2 \quad ((7))$$

Thus, the strange average involved in $P(p/x)$ and $P(x/p)$ dictates the form of the spatial density $P(x)$ (and also of $P(p)$). $P(p/x)$ is involved in a resonance equation (the Schrodinger equation) which seems to be based on spatial frequencies p , a p momentum state kinetic energy based on the change in the change of the two channels in space as well as the potential $V(x)$ being written in terms of $V_k \exp(ikx)$. This resonance solution, however, then leads to physical consequences for spatial density and flows within the system.

Conclusion

By examining an expression for kinetic energy at a point x in a quantum bound system, one sees that p momentum state kinetic energies, $p^2/2m$, may carry a negative weight. Thus, they subtract kinetic energy from the average. If kinetic energy is a quantity or substance, it seems difficult to interpret this behavior. On the other hand, if one assumes a quantum particle is involved in a two channel process, linked periodically in space, i.e. $\exp(ipx) = \cos(px) + i\sin(px)$, then single particle kinetic energy may be interpreted as the change in the change of $\exp(ipx)$ in space and not as a quantity. A quantum resonance is established in terms of properties of this two channel system because the potential may also be written as a Fourier series and so also contains $\exp(ikx)$ terms. Overall, the resonance energy E in the Schrodinger equation is also related to a frequency in time. Thus, kinetic energy may not be a quantity, but rather is linked to spatial frequency. In the quantum resonance, however, these frequencies and changes etc have direct consequences for physical observables

such as spatial density W^2 and flows. In fact, the quantum average of momentum is related to spatial changes in physical density.